

Synthesis of 2,6-Dimethyl-10(*p*-tolyl)-2,6(*E*)-undecadiene

O. P. VIG, S. D. KUMAR, SUKHJIT SINGH and RASHMI VIG

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh-160 014

Manuscript received 10 July 1978, revised 20 November 1978, accepted 11 January 1979

Starting from 4-methyl-8(*p*-tolyl)-4(*E*)-nonen-1-al obtained through the Claisen rearrangement of a properly substituted vinyl ether followed by Wittig reaction with isopropylidene-triphenylphosphorane, a new synthesis of 2,6-dimethyl-10(*p*-tolyl)-2,6(*E*)-undecadiene have been accomplished.

COLLINS et al¹ isolated and characterised a monocyclic diterpene hydrocarbon isomeric with artemesene² from the essential oil of *Salvia dorisiana*, a herbaceous plant native to Honduras. It was assigned structure (I) on the basis of detailed spectral studies¹ including NMR, IR and Mass. Further confirmation has been provided by synthesis³.

However, in the present communication, we wish to report a new synthesis of the racemate of the title compound through the application of Claisen rearrangement of properly substituted allyl vinyl

ether, coupled with Wittig reaction⁴ for the unambiguous fixation of the olefinic bonds in the desired positions.

The aldehyde(II), the starting material for the projected synthesis, was prepared according to the method of Buchi et al⁵. It was subjected to Grignard reaction with isopropenylmagnesium bromide in THF when the allylic carbinol(III) was obtained in 80% yield which was smoothly transformed into the vinyl ether(IV) through equilibration⁶ with ethyl vinyl ether in the presence of freshly crystallised mercuric acetate as a catalyst. The chromatographically pure vinyl ether was submitted to pyrolysis in a half-filled sealed tube in nitrogen atmosphere when it generated the unsaturated aldehyde(V) in 66% yield. Triply substituted double bond in the aldehyde(V) is assigned a *E*-configuration in view of earlier observations^{7,8} that a similarly substituted vinyl ether when migrated forms a *E*-trisubstituted bond. Wittig reaction with isopropylidene-triphenylphosphorane on (V) furnished the title hydrocarbon (I) in 70% yield whose spectral properties (IR, NMR, MS) were identical to those published¹.

Experimental

All boiling points are uncorrected. IR spectra ($\nu_{\max}$ in cm^{-1}) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer with sodium chloride optics using thin films. NMR spectrum was recorded at 80 MHz using TMS as an internal standard. Unless otherwise stated all organic extracts were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Purity of all samples was checked by thin layer chromatography. Neutral alumina was used for column chromatography.

2-Methyl-6(*p*-tolyl)-1-hepten-3-ol (III) :

To the Grignard reagent, prepared from magnesium turnings (700 mg.) and isopropenylbromide (5 g) in dry THF (200 ml), was added dropwise a solution of 4(*p*-tolyl)-pentan-1-al (II, 4.41 g) in THF (20 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred well for 2 hr and left overnight at room tempera-

ture. It was then decomposed with a saturated solution of ammonium chloride and worked up in the usual manner. The crude product obtained after removal of the solvent was chromatographed over alumina with ether and was further purified by distillation under reduced pressure to produce (III), b. p. 140-145°/8-10 mm, yield 4 g (80%). IR : 3400, 1640, 1050, 895, 820. (Found ; C, 82.90 ; H, 9.59. $C_{15}H_{21}O$ requires C, 82.95 ; H, 9.67%.)

2-Methyl-6(p-tolyl)-3-vinyloxy-hepten-1 (IV) :

A mixture of alcohol (III, 3.9 g), ethyl vinyl ether (39 ml) and freshly crystallised mercuric acetate (750 mg) was heated under reflux for 10 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled in ice cold bath and stirred for 30 min. with cold sodium carbonate solution (10%, 50 ml). The organic phase was separated, washed with water and dried (K_2CO_3). The excess vinyl ether was removed and the residue was chromatographed on alumina. Elution with petroleum ether (40-60°) gave pure vinyl ether (IV), b.p. 131-135°/8-10 mm, yield 3.0 g (77%). IR : 1650, 1610, 1600, 985, 900, 820 (Found : C, 83.0 ; H, 9.80. $C_{17}H_{24}O$ requires C, 83.6, H, 9.83%.)

4-Methyl-8 (p-tolyl)-4 (E)-nonen-1-al (V) :

The vinyl ether (3.0 g) was heated for 30 min. at 175° in an atmosphere of nitrogen in a half-filled sealed tube, fully immersed, in an oil bath. Distillation afforded the aldehyde (V), b.p. 137-139°/8-10 mm, yield 2.0 g (66%). IR : 2710, 1720, 900, 820. (Found : C, 83.0 ; H, 9.80. $C_{17}H_{24}O$ requires C, 83.6 ; H, 9.86%.)

2,6-Dimethyl-10(p-tolyl)-2, 6(E)-undecadiene (I) :

A solution of methyl sulphinyl carbanion was prepared under nitrogen atmosphere as usual, from sodium hydride (393 mg) and dimethylsulphoxide

(3 ml). This on treatment with isopropyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (3.5 g) in dimethylsulphoxide (6 ml) in cold gave deep red coloured phosphorane. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 10 min. To this was added the aldehyde (V, 1 g) in THF (5 ml). The contents were stirred for 2 hr. and then left overnight at room temperature. The contents were poured in crushed ice and worked up as usual. The crude product after removal of the solvent was chromatographed over alumina when elution with petroleum ether (40-60°) gave the pure hydrocarbon, yield : 700 mg (70%). IR : 3040, 1510, 820. NMR(δ) : 7.02 (4H, aromatic protons), 5.07 (2H, trisubstituted olefinic protons), 2.0(3H, aromatic methyl). The remaining protons appear between 0.9-2.0. Mass : Parent ion peak at m/e 270, other prominent peaks were m/e 145, 132, 119, 105, 91, 69 and 41. (Found : C, 88.60 ; H, 11.0. $C_{20}H_{30}$ requires C, 88.88 ; H, 11.11%.)

References

1. A. F. HALIM and R. P. COLLINS, *J. Agriculture and Food Chemistry*, 1975, **23**, 506.
2. SORM ET AL., *Chem. Listy*, 1951, **45**, 195 ; *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1951, **16**, 268.
3. O. P. VIG, I. R. TREHAN and (Miss) RITA KUMAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, (Communicated).
4. R. GREENWALD, M. CHAYKOVSKY and E. J. CORRY, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 1128.
5. G. BUCHI and H. WURST, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1969, **34**, 1122.
6. W. H. WATANABE and L. E. CONLON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 2828.
7. O. P. VIG, J. C. KAPUR, (Miss) C. K. KHURANA and B. VIG, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 505.
8. D. J. FAULKNER and M. R. PETERSEN, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1969, 3243-3246.